

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE 7. KEY RESOURCES TABLE

REAGENT RESOURCE	or	SOURCE	IDENTIFIER
Experimental models : Organisms/Strains			
C57Bl/6		Charles River	027
B6.129S4(Cg)- Arntl ^{tm1} Weit/J (Bmal1 ^{flox/flox})		The Jackson Laboratory	#:007668
LC1-Cre		(1)	N/A
Pax8-rtTA		(1)	N/A
Bmal1 ^{flox/flox} Pax8-rtTA	LC1-Cre	This paper	
Reagents			
Phosphate Buffer 10X pH 7.4		Gibco	70011-044
Doxycycline Hyclate		Appllichem	A2951
Standard diet		Kliba-Nafag	3242
Data			
RNA-seq data		This paper	GSE216252
Proteomics data		This paper	PXD036803 (Proteomexchange.org)
Metabolomics data		This paper	doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7225427
Softwares and Algorithms			
GraphPad Prism		GraphPad Software, LCC	v9.4.0
Xcalibur		ThermoFisher Scientific	v4.2
MaxQuant		Max-Planck-Institute of Biochemistry	v.1.6.14.0
Perseus		(2)	1.6.5.0
IMOD		Electron microscopy facility University of Lausanne	v4.10.35
bcl2fastq2		Illumina, Inc.	v2.20
Cutadapt		https://doi.org/10.14806/ej.17.1.200	v1.8
fastq_screen		(3)	v0.11.1
reaper		(3)	v15-065
STAR		(4)	v2.5.3a

htseq-count	(4)	v0.9.1
R	https://www.r-project.org/	v4.0.3, v4.1.0
Bioconductor (R packages for bioinformatics)	https://bioconductor.org/ , (5)	v3.12, v3.13
dryR	(6) https://github.com/naef-lab/dryR	v1.0.0
edgeR	(7) https://doi.org/10.18129/B9.bioc.edgeR	
STAR	(8) https://code.google.com/archive/p/rna-star/	v. 2.5.3a

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